

Supplementary Material for the Manuscript

“Transient Stability Assessment of Power Systems via Neural Lyapunov Functions and Fault-Space PAC Safety Certificates”

Yuqing Lin, Tianhao Wen, Mengshi Li, and Q. H. Wu

Submitted to IEEE Transactions on Power Systems

This document provides the appendices referenced throughout the manuscript. Owing to the IEEE PES ten-page limit at submission, these appendices are made available here as online supplementary material. They are cited in the manuscript as Appendix A through Appendix G.

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Appendix A: State-Space of IEEE 9-Bus System

The IEEE 3-machine 9-bus system operates under the sixth-order subtransient generator model, in which each machine is governed by the state vector $[\delta, \omega, E'_q, E'_d, E_{fd}, P_m]^\top$. Taking machine 1 as the angular reference and eliminating its absolute rotor angle δ_1 yields a 17-dimensional relative state

$$\mathbf{x} = [\omega_1, E'_{q,1}, E'_{d,1}, E_{fd,1}, P_{m,1}, \delta_{21}, \omega_2, E'_{q,2}, E'_{d,2}, E_{fd,2}, P_{m,2}, \delta_{31}, \omega_3, E'_{q,3}, E'_{d,3}, E_{fd,3}, P_{m,3}]^\top,$$

where $\delta_{i1} = \delta_i - \delta_1$. The relative coordinate system ensures that the post-restoration equilibrium \mathbf{x}^* is uniquely defined and that the autonomous system (1) is well-posed for stability analysis. The instability criterion is $\max_i |\delta_{i1}| \geq 2\pi$.

Appendix B: Fault Parameter Space and Data Generation of IEEE 9-Bus System

The fault parameter space Θ is constructed by a full Cartesian product scan:

TABLE I: Fault Parameter Space for the IEEE 9-Bus System

Parameter	Values	Count
Faulted line index k	{4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9}	6
Fractional fault location ℓ	{0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0}	5
Fault impedance Z_f (Ω)	{0.001, 0.05, 0.2}	3
Clearing time t_c (s)	0.06 : 0.01 : 0.30	25
Dead time Δt (s)	0.50 : 0.05 : 1.50	21

This yields $6 \times 5 \times 3 \times 25 \times 21 = 47,250$ contingencies, all of which complete simulation successfully. Among these, 45,546 are stable and 1,704 are unstable (3.61%).

For trajectory sampling, rather than storing entire post-restoration trajectories, representative state–vector-field pairs are extracted per contingency. For stable scenarios, samples are drawn at the reclosure instant, uniformly within $[0, 1]$ s, at local extrema of the maximum absolute rotor deviation, and at proportional late-trajectory instants. For unstable scenarios, uniform samples are drawn from the feasible segment prior to the first violation of $|\delta_{i1}| = 2\pi$. This procedure produces 863,404 samples in total (average 18.3 per contingency), summarized below.

TABLE II: Dataset Split Statistics

Split	Total	Stable	Unstable
Training	518,051	515,631	2,420
Calibration	172,353	171,552	801
Test	173,000	172,137	863

Splitting is performed at the contingency level (60%/20%/20%) so that all samples from a given scenario belong to exactly one partition.

Appendix C: Neural Lyapunov Network and Training Hyperparameters of IEEE 9-Bus System

1) Preprocessing. The quadratic backbone matrix \mathbf{P}_0 is obtained by solving the continuous Lyapunov equation at \mathbf{x}^* . The compression scale c_0 is estimated as the median of $q(\mathbf{x})$ over 200 randomly drawn stable training samples, yielding $c_0 = 0.2741$. The IQR scaling matrix \mathbf{D} is computed from the interquartile range of each state dimension across all training samples.

2) Network architecture and hyperparameters. The neural correction branch $\phi_\psi : \mathbb{R}^{17} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4$ uses two hidden layers of widths 32 and 16 with tanh activations. Spectral normalization is applied to all linear layers, enforcing $\text{Lip}(\phi_\psi) \leq 1$. The blending coefficient α is initialized at 0.6 and constrained to $[0.05, 0.9]$ throughout training. More hyperparameters are shown below.

TABLE III: Loss and Optimization Hyperparameters

Hyperparameter	Value
Hidden layers	[32, 16]
Output dimension k	4
Separation margin Δ	0.02
Stable class weight w_s	1.0
Unstable class weight w_u	10.0
Negativity decay rate η_{train}	0.01
Separation loss weight λ_{sep}	1.0
Negativity loss weight λ_{ψ}	2.0

4) Optimization. The Adam optimizer is used with learning rate 10^{-3} . Each epoch draws 16 mini-batches; each mini-batch contains 8,192 stable samples and 1,024 unstable samples (ratio 8:1). Training uses mixed-precision (AMP) on CUDA with random seed 42. The learning rate scheduler (decay factor 0.5, patience 3, minimum 10^{-5}) and early stopping (patience 6, $\delta_{\min} = 10^{-4}$, best-weight restoration) together terminate training at epoch 37, with best weights from epoch 31.

TABLE IV: Training Outcomes

Metric	Value
Best calibration loss	1.52×10^{-3}
Final α	0.7058
Train stable $V \leq 1 - \Delta$	99.75%
Train unstable $V \geq 1 + \Delta$	99.97%
Train stable $\dot{V} + \eta V \leq 0$	98.63%
Empirical Lipschitz estimate (test set)	28.21

Appendix D: PAC Calibration Details of IEEE 9-Bus System

The candidate threshold set is $\mathcal{C} = 0.90, 0.91, \dots, 1.10$ with $|\mathcal{C}| = 11$. With $\alpha_{\text{risk}} = 0.10$, $\beta = 0.05$, and $N_u = 801$ unstable calibration contingencies, the corrected bound evaluates to $\bar{\alpha} = 0.10 - \sqrt{\ln(11/0.05)/(2 \times 801)} = 0.0580$. Seven candidates satisfy $\hat{\alpha}(c) \leq \bar{\alpha}$, and the lexicographic rule (25) selects $c^* = 0.98$. The test-set certificate performance at $c^* = 0.98$ is: FAR = 0.0%, stable coverage = 98.96%.

Appendix E: Transient Energy Function and PEBS-Based CCT Estimation of IEEE 9-Bus System

The TEF/PEBS baseline adopts the classical reduced-order approximation of the IEEE 9-bus system. Starting from the full sixth-order DAE model, three simplifications are applied: (i) AVR and governor dynamics are frozen at their pre-fault equilibrium values, reducing each machine to a second-order swing equation; (ii) each machine is represented by a constant internal voltage E'_i behind its transient reactance $X'_{d,i}$; (iii) the network is Kron-reduced to the internal generator nodes, and the lossless approximation retains only the imaginary part of the reduced admittance matrix. Under these assumptions, the post-fault dynamics take the form

$$M_i \dot{\omega}_i = P_{m,i} - P_{e,i}(\delta) - D_i(\omega_i - \omega_s), \quad \dot{\delta}_i = \omega_i - \omega_s,$$

with $M_i = 2H_i/\omega_s$. The corresponding post-fault potential energy is

$$U_{\text{post}}(\delta) = - \sum_i P_{e,i}^* (\delta_i - \delta_i^*) - \sum_{i < j} E'_i E'_j B_{ij}^{\text{post}} [\cos \delta_{ij} - \cos \delta_{ij}^*]$$

where $B_{ij}^{\text{post}} = \text{Im}(Y_{\text{red},ij}^{\text{post}})$ and $P_{e,i}^*$ is the equilibrium electrical power injection under the lossless approximation, chosen to enforce $\nabla \delta U_{\text{post}}(\delta^*) = 0$. The kinetic energy is measured in the center-of-inertia (COI) frame,

$$T(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i M_i (\omega_i - \omega_{\text{COI}})^2, \quad \omega_{\text{COI}} = \frac{\sum_i M_i \omega_i}{\sum_i M_i},$$

giving the total energy

$$W(\delta, \omega) = T(\omega) + U_{\text{post}}(\delta)$$

with $W(\delta^*, \omega_s) = 0$.

The critical energy W_{cr} is taken as the minimum potential energy over all type-1 saddle points (unstable equilibrium points, UEPs) of U_{post} , located numerically via gradient search and classified by the Hessian signature. The PEBS-estimated CCT is the largest clearing time t_c for which $W(\delta_c, \omega_c) \leq W_{\text{cr}}$, evaluated at the fault-clearing state (δ_c, ω_c) obtained from full time-domain simulation. The scanning resolution is $\Delta t_{\text{scan}} = 0.01$ s, matching the TDS reference. Over 100 test scenarios, this procedure yields MRE = 35.6%, with the estimates systematically conservative due to the lossless network approximation.

Appendix F: Scalability Comparison Across Methods

The scalability comparison in Table I reflects two orthogonal dimensions: the analysis mode (per-fault versus unified) and the growth of computational cost with system size.

1) Analysis mode. TDS and TEF/PEBS are inherently per-fault methods: each new contingency requires an independent ODE integration or a fresh energy-function evaluation starting from the fault-clearing state. Deep MLP, Plain NLF and the proposed method all operate in unified mode: once trained offline, any contingency is assessed by a single forward pass, with no per-fault simulation required at deployment.

2) Growth with state dimension. TEF/PEBS relies on an analytical energy function whose construction requires explicit Kron reduction and UEP search; both steps become increasingly unreliable as the number of machines grows, and the lossless network approximation incurs growing model error in large, lossy systems. SOS-based Lyapunov alternatives (not included as baselines here) suffer from polynomial degree growth with n , making them intractable beyond moderate state dimensions. Deep MLP, Plain NLF, and the proposed method all scale gracefully in both training and inference: the network size grows approximately linearly with the state dimension (e.g., hidden layers widen from [32, 16] in the 17-state case to [128, 64] in the 56-state case) and remains computationally tractable. The distinction among these three methods lies not in training cost but in the certification step. Deep MLP and Plain NLF provide no formal certification mechanism, so whether the trained model remains adequate at a larger scale can only be assessed empirically. The proposed method, by contrast, supplements the same graceful neural

network scaling with a PAC calibration (Algorithm 2) whose complexity is independent of the state dimension, as detailed below.

3) Calibration complexity of the proposed method. The PAC calibration (Algorithm 2) requires the number of unstable calibration contingencies to satisfy $N_u > \ln(|\mathcal{C}|/\beta)/(2\alpha_{\text{risk}}^2)$, a threshold that depends only on $|\mathcal{C}|$, α_{risk} , and β , and is entirely independent of the state dimension n . For the settings used in this paper ($\alpha_{\text{risk}} = 0.10$, $\beta = 0.05$, $|\mathcal{C}| = 11$), the requirement is $N_u > 337$. This remains unchanged whether the system has 17 or 170 state variables. Consequently, the certificate guarantee of Theorem 1 can be obtained with a calibration effort that does not scale with system complexity—a property shared by neither TEF/PEBS nor any of the other baselines.

Appendix G: Modified IEEE 39-Bus System Details

1) State-space. The modified system retains the sixth-order subtransient model $[\delta, \omega, E'_q, E'_d, E_{fd}, P_m]^\top$ for nine synchronous generators (G1–G10 except G2) and replaces the generator G2 with a grid-forming inverter governed by $[\delta, \omega, E'_q]^\top$ (virtual angle, angular frequency, and internal voltage; consider Q-V droop control and current limiting). The full system has $9 \times 6 + 3 = 57$ differential states. Taking G10 as the angular reference and eliminating its absolute angle yields a 56-dimensional relative state:

$$x = [\delta_{i,10}, \omega_i, E'_{q,i}, E'_{d,i}, E_{fd,i}, P_{m,i}]^\top,$$

where $\delta_{i,10} = \delta_i - \delta_{10}$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, 10$. Note that $E'_{d,2}, E_{fd,2}, P_{m,2}, \delta_{10,10}$ are abandoned. The instability criterion is $\max_i |\delta_{i,10}| \geq 2\pi$.

2) Fault parameter space. The fault parameter grid is listed in Table V. The full Cartesian product yields $35 \times 5 \times 3 \times 23 \times 11 = 132,825$ contingencies, of which 132,711 complete simulation successfully (123,843 stable, 8,868 unstable). Trajectory sampling follows Case A, producing 1,651,826 labeled samples split at the contingency level into training (79,626 contingencies), calibration (26,542), and test (26,543) sets.

TABLE V: Fault Parameter Space for IEEE 39-Bus System

Parameter	Values	Count
Faulted line index k	Except generator outlet lines	35
Fractional fault location ℓ	{0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0}	5
Fault impedance Z_f (Ω)	{0.001, 0.01, 0.05}	3
Clearing time t_c (s)	0.08 : 0.01 : 0.30	23
Dead time Δt (s)	0.50 : 0.10 : 1.50	11

3) Network architecture and training hyperparameters. The key hyperparameters are listed in Table VI. Compared with the 9-bus case, the wider hidden layers ([128, 64] versus [32, 16]) and higher output dimension ($k = 8$ versus $k = 4$) provide the additional expressive capacity needed for the 56-dimensional state space. The negativity decay rate $\eta_{\text{train}} = 0.05$ is moderately larger than in Case A (0.01) to encourage steeper Lyapunov descent. Training terminates at epoch 98 with best weights from epoch 92; the final blending coefficient is $\alpha = 0.392$.

4) PAC calibration. The candidate threshold set is $\mathcal{C} = \{0.90, 0.92, \dots, 1.10\}$ with $|\mathcal{C}| = 11$. With $\alpha_{\text{risk}} = 0.03$,

TABLE VI: Hyperparameters of the Lyapunov learning

Hyperparameter	Value
Hidden layers	[128, 64]
Output dimension k	8
Activation	tanh
Blending coefficient α range / init	[0.05, 0.9] / 0.5
Separation margin Δ	0.02
Class weights w_s / w_u	1.0 / 10.0
Negativity decay rate η_{train}	0.05
Loss weights $\lambda_{\text{sep}} / \lambda_{\hat{V}}$	1.0 / 2.0
Mini-batch size (stable / unstable)	24,576 / 3,072
Learning rate	10^{-3} (Adam)

$\beta = 0.01$, and $N_u = 1,763$ unstable calibration contingencies, the corrected bound evaluates to $\bar{\alpha} = 0.03 - \sqrt{\ln(11/0.01)/(2 \times 1763)} = 0.009$. Eight candidates satisfy $\hat{\alpha}(c) \leq \bar{\alpha}$; the lexicographic rule selects $c^* = 1.00$. Key calibration points are listed in Table VII. The test-set performance at $c^* = 1.00$ is: FAR = 0%, stable coverage = 95.02%.

TABLE VII: Calibration Results at Selected Thresholds

Threshold c	Coverage (cal.)	FAR (cal.)
0.90	91.58%	0.0%
0.98	94.78%	0.0%
1.00	95.02%	0.0%
1.02	95.14%	0.074%
1.04	95.23%	0.333%